

UCIAN Nursing Graduates Learned Competencies and Employability Mapping in the Healthcare Sector

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Abstract

m needs to trace the relevance of its curriculum to the requirements of the healthcare industry where its graduates intend to work or exercise their profession. This study determined the employability of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates for th school years 2017-2020, with the purpose of developing the

program-level intervention plan to strengthen the educational services provided to the students. This study utilized the descriptive survey research design with twenty-two (22) Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad from 2017 to July 2020. This study was conducted at organizations

or healthcare institutions where the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of UC-Banilad were employed during the survey. The instrument used in this study is the modified CHED Graduate Tracer Study [GTS] survey questionnaire. The administration of the Graduate Tracer Tool (GTS) together with the Informed Consent Form was done using the Google Form in which the link was submitted through the Facebook Messenger of the BSN alumni. There were also target respondents who visited the University, and they accomplished the survey tool, and retrieval was done after that. The simple percentage, weighted mean was used to analyze the data. The researchers ensured that the ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and autonomy were adhered to in the conduct.

The result shows that more of the graduate respondents belonged to the age bracket of 24 to 25 years old, graduated in 2019, took the BSN degree because they were inspired by a role model, attended the Intravenous Training and Blood Transfusion, while the majority of of them were females, single, passed the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination (PNLE) and pursued advanced studies for professional development. In terms of employment status, more of them had regular or permanent jobs, were able to find a job in less than a month through information from friends, and earned a gross monthly income of Php20,000.00 to below Php 25,000.00. At the same time, those who were unemployed revealed that they pursued advanced studies. On the other hand, they worked locally as professionals and viewed the BSN program of UC as relevant to

their first job and that their job was related to the BSN course. Predominantly, they learned communication skills that they learned in college as useful in their first job, they accepted the job because of the salaries and benefits.

Moreover, the respondents divulged that they greatly manifested the College of Nursing's vision as a leading producer of accessible and quality nursing; the College of Nursing's mission to maintain a healthy educational setting that fosters quality; the College of Nursing's goals in adapting competency standards in instruction learning resources, and educational services, promoting leadership among faculty in the service of the community, and fostering a pool of highly motivated competent and compassionate faculty and students in the pursuit of personal and professional development; the College of Nursing core values (nurturing, unity, respect, service, excellence); the BSN Program Educational Objectives (PEOs), stipulations in the CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15, Series of 2017 for Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] program and the performance indicators for the BSN program. Moreover, they greatly attained the BSN Program Outcomes (POs). Therefore, the graduates of the BSN program of UC-Banilad for the school years 2017 to 2020 were employable in different healthcare entities and could practice their nursing profession. Likewise, they exhibited the nurse's desired competencies and graduate attributes, indicating that the curriculum is in line with the established requirements by the regulatory bodies and the healthcare industry.

Keywords: *Health pedagogy, curriculum review, employability, Bachelor of Science in Nursing, descriptive, Cebu City*

INTRODUCTION

A nation's economy runs on the knowledge and skills of its people. This indicates that the country's workforce's personal and professional development is critical to nation-building (Ramirez et al., 2014). Modern society brings uncertainty and fluidity to the World of Work (WoW), with fast-paced

changes, volatile professions, and disruptive and shifting standards for being employable (Bauman, 2007). It can then be said that higher education contributes significantly to graduates' personal and professional development. In the twenty-first century, aside from technical knowledge, well-developed personal and professional skills are essential traits to have in order to compete for and keep a job in the global industrial market (Ismail & Mohammed, 2015).

Education is a critical tool for empowerment in terms of socioeconomic, political, and technical growth (Van, 2020). Knowledge gained in higher education is frequently contextualized and recontextualized in the health sector (Billet et al., 2014). Every academic institution aims to produce competent and highly qualified graduates who can eventually compete locally or globally (Hipona et al., 2021).

Bell (2010) explains that quality graduates become excellent in their field of expertise, which will be evident in workplace performances in the future. Hence, colleges, schools, and universities must provide education and training to meet the standards of different industry employers set for their specific workforce. Other industries must set different standards, but they would always have characteristics they expect their applicants to possess that would boost institutional objectives (Abbot & Snidal, 2021).

Every year, colleges and universities all over the country turn to society, a graduate ready to enter the world. However, how are they prepared to face life? Is a diploma enough to guarantee that they will find a stable job? Every year, higher educational institutions produce fresh graduates ready for the job market (Almejas et al., 2017). People with education who are significantly self-sufficient and independent with all the skills needed to practice different professions would become fully equipped with different world economic instability (Orejana & Resurrection, 2010).

Nursing education programs aim to facilitate the development of competent, safe, caring novice nurses who can adapt to and influence the ever-changing practice environment. Nursing educators strive to make the student's educational experience engaging and meaningful, using the best available teaching and learning evidence. Ongoing quality improvement initiatives, or at times more significant curricular renewal projects, are deemed necessary (Landeem et al., 2016).

Higher education in general, and nursing education in particular, have been called upon to facilitate deep knowing, moving beyond the accumulation of knowledge (Barnett, 2009; Benner et al., 2010). Quality education makes a difference in nursing practice. Baccalaureate nursing programs provide an in-depth knowledge of physical and social sciences, research, leadership and management, community nursing, and humanities. This enhances nursing graduates' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in dealing with patients and providing healthcare (Johnson, 2009).

In the 21st century, employability is the most required skill besides technical, practical, and analytical skills to compete for employment and sustain jobs in the global industrial market (Ismail & Mohammed, 2015). As a measure of accountability and demonstration of impact, these educational institutions must show forth their graduates' employability profile, as well as the impact these institutions have on the graduates' personal and professional development (Dewi et al., 2021; Hazaymeh & Dela Peña, 2017).

One of the success indicators of higher educational institutions (HEIs) is the quality of its graduates, which is translated into employability. Although no formula will ensure success during graduates' transition into employment (Hinchliffe & Jolly, 2013), employability constantly measures their quality and value (Jayasingam et al., 2016). Undeniably, employability can be best measured by a program's alumni as they are considered the finest proof of the program's performance (Aquino et al., 2015).

Nowadays, finding employment is as challenging as finding a needle in a haystack. Moreover, many nursing graduates are noted to have work unrelated to their college course (Sanchez & Diamante, 2017). In the past, nurses' employability had been a national problem, as evidenced by the bulk of nursing graduates employed outside the jurisdiction of their profession. Recently, the scenario changed its course, as employers struggled their way into the portals of the academe as they tried to run after graduating students who would soon join the decreasing number of nurses in the workforce.

In the U.S., more than 3.1 million registered nurses are practicing the profession nationwide, with a faster growth in employment than most other occupations in 2018 (American Association of Colleges of Nursing, 2019). Between 2001 and 2004, 43,897 nurses sought employment abroad, a number higher than the nurses who made their way into the workforce at the same time after obtaining their licenses. During this period, despite an oversupply of nurses, there needed to be a nurse-patient ratio due to the underfunding of the health system and the lack of health facilities. A report from a news agency even mentioned that around 200,000 nurses were unemployed in 2016 (Trines, 2018).

One of the problems the Philippines faces today is unemployment. The unemployment rate of the Philippines in 2012 was 7.20%, one of the highest among Asian countries in the last five years (Gonzales, 2013). Unemployed Filipino nurses are estimated to be 187,000 (Howard, 2010). The unemployment rate in the Philippines dropped to 5.50 percent in the second quarter of 2018 from 5.70 percent in the previous year, with an increase in the number of employed individuals from 625 thousand to 40.9 million. The Philippines' unemployment rate averaged 8.44 percent from 1994 until 2018, obtaining an all-time high of 13.90 percent in the first quarter of 2000 and a record low of 4.70 percent in the fourth quarter of 2016 (Trading Economics, 2019).

This situation challenges the traditionally dominating approach of possessional employability (Holmes, 2015). In this approach, employability is often defined as the possession of certain characteristics, skills, or capabilities (Holmes, 2015; Okay-Somerville & Scholarios, 2017), and the emphasis is often on the needs of the job market (Crisp et al., 2019) viewed from a cross-sectional instead of a longitudinal perspective (Fleuren et al., 2020).

The focus on assessing student learning outcomes is not new in the nursing education literature and is regarded as a necessary component of nursing curricular development (Billings & Halstead; Iwasiw & Goldenberg, 2015; Keating, 2014). Graduate tracer studies are essential for understanding the relevance and quality of programs offered by universities and the labor market (Sanchez & Diamante, 2017).

In the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education requires all Higher Education Institutions [HEIs] to conduct a tracer study. It is equally reflected as one of the required documents by any higher education accrediting body, such as the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP), Inc. for government and the private sector Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges and Universities [PAASCU] (Hipona et al., 2021) and Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges and Universities [PAASCU].

The alumni are an excellent source of feedback regarding the program's relevance in the current labor market. Moreover, they are considered the best evidence of a program's effectiveness in employment and positions (Orejana & Resurrection, 2010).

Considering the vast and rapidly increasing number of students attending higher education, looking into the appraisal (Almejas et al., 2017) by the College of Nursing, where they attained their bachelor's degree, is timely. The experiences graduates encounter in their workplace provide an excellent reference for checking and balancing the institution's quality of education. This is one way of looking at a realistic perspective of what needs to be done to achieve the educational objectives set by the program and the college (Du et al., 2019). Thus, the challenge of employability of the graduates and aligning the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) curriculum to the nursing profession and the standards of practice in the healthcare industry can be addressed.

By conducting a survey on the cohort of graduates from a specific institution, profession, discipline, level of education, their employment characteristics, competencies, and skills development, and conducting a comparative analysis, the information gained from these can be used by the graduate's alma mater and other education stakeholders for curriculum development and other emerging reforms. Because of their nature, graduate tracer studies typically have similar objectives, such as finding out the results of higher education and training in terms of employment outcomes to improve higher education provision (Hipona et al., 2021). Hence, this study aims to trace Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the

University of Cebu-Banilad, School Year 2017-2020, to be able to formulate a proposed program-level intervention plan.

Framework

This investigation is focused on the USEM Model of Knight and Yorke (2004), which identifies four key components comprising understanding (U), skilled practice (S), efficacy beliefs (E), and metacognition (M). A vital feature of the model is that the efficacy beliefs provide a foundation for employability and feed the U, S, and M components. The E component represents a person's belief that they can impact a situation. It includes a broad range of theoretical contributions. Likewise, The USEM model of Knight and Yorke denotes the set of understanding, skills, and personal attributes – efficacy and metacognition; a gateway for individuals to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupation, which benefits themselves, the workforce, the community, and the economy (Oliver, 2015; Paadi, 2014).

The USEM model was created for the Skills Plus Project, assessment, learning, and workforce, and it aimed to theorize learning outcomes through employability settings (Soares et al., 2017). This focused on students' understanding and skills based on efficacy and metacognition. Higher education institutions should pay more attention to the personal qualities of the subject (Soares et al., 2016).

The USEM model is widely considered a significant development in employability research since, for the first time, employability was conceptualized concerning other constructs such as skills, subject understanding metacognition, and personal qualities. This model also provides a framework for embedding employability into the curriculum and acknowledges the needs of students, employers, and other stakeholders into considerations (Cole & Tibby, 2012).

Experience can also be used to develop a student's self-efficacy, a critical component of the USEM model. Ways of influencing efficacy development are mastery and vicarious experiences (Bandura, 1995). The work of Knight and Yorke has been vital in developing a definition and model of employability for higher education [HE] (Showcross & Ridgman, 2012).

All Higher Education Institution's (HEIs) objectives are to create proficient and highly trained graduates who can eventually set out in life no matter the situation or the economic stability of the country they are in (Torres & Schugurensky, 2002). Thus, the education and training every graduate can get would ensure better opportunities for all individuals to develop their skills in the lifelong learning perspective, enabling them to adapt to rapidly changing labor market requirements and different conditions (Leberman & McDonald, 2016; Taylor & Hamdy, 2013).

The notion of employability has risen to prominence over the past 20 years, gaining remarkable traction in policy-making, organizational life, and society. The term has become popular as an antipode to the policy goal of 'full employment' (Finn, 2000) and the conceptual lynchpin of a new career covenant that claims to supplant long-term organizational career bargains (Kanter, 1989).

The central concept for an employability model is the capability, or the necessary part of specialist expertise is knowing their specialism; they also have the confidence to apply their knowledge and skill within the varied and changing situation to continue developing their knowledge and skills (Sumanasiri, 2011). The personal driving force of individuals to do the job they love is their economic development. This also relates to the past learning and skills acquired through education and being taught in school and the addition of experiences through the practice of the profession after graduation (Schleicher, 2012).

In different streams of literature, employability has been defined in different, often related ways. It takes an interdisciplinary approach, combining insights from research on higher education and workplace learning, taking a Western perspective (Romgens et al., 2019).

Graduate employability in context: Theory, research and Debate' highlighted employability's complex, contentious, and multi-faceted nature as a concept and policy (Fakunle & Hingson, 2021). Graduate employability is a set of achievements – skills, understanding, and personal attributes – that makes a graduate more likely to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupations' (Yorke, 2006).

Focusing on employability is an attempt to influence the supply side of the labor market, i.e., the workplace and the productive capacities and performance. In contrast, the demand side comprises the company's requirements, which depend on the growth dynamic (Weiner et al., 2017).

In this capacity, 'employability' gestures to a new arrangement wherein the state and employers are no longer committed to nor deemed responsible for providing those they govern and/or employ with lasting and secure jobs. Instead, individuals' capacity to take the initiative, relentlessly update and improve their knowledge and skills, and be flexible and adaptable, i.e., to work on their employability constantly, has come to be understood as the crux of national, organizational, and individual prosperity (Chertkovskaya et al., 2013).

Moreover, according to Dumlao (2006), employability is the capacity to meet the minimum requirement for a special kind of work or employment position. The occupational opportunities and the nature of the job obtained after graduation speak of the employability of graduates. The effectiveness can be judged according to the graduates' success or failure to use their acquired skills and training in economics. Progress. Likewise, Brown and Hesketh (2004) defined employability as the relative chances of getting and maintaining different kinds of employment.

Employability is primarily conceived as a measurable economic outcome for graduates and institutions. This points out both the importance of graduates as critical contributors to economic development and the role of higher education in facilitating the development of graduates for the labor market. At the same time, the seeming consensus regarding employability as an outcome concerning employment or employment rates belies the complexity surrounding the concept in the broader literature. Early on, we want to point out that, related to this complexity, we acknowledge that higher education institutions' educational, research, and service aims are not limited to developing graduate employability (Agasisti et al., 2011; McCowan, 2015).

Williams et al. (2016) suggested that the literature emphasizes three dimensions of employability: capital components, career management, and contextual components. The capital components include human capital (skills the individual possesses that enhance economic productivity), social and cultural capital, and psychological capital. Psychological capital is related to how employability can be enhanced by individual characteristics, such as 'confidence, hope resilience, positive self-evaluation and personality traits such as conscientiousness' Career management has two parts: signal management and self-management. Both aspects reiterate the importance of the individual's ability to navigate the world of employment concerning job acquisition and relevant training (Luthans, 2002).

Employability is practiced in different circumstances; the first is through learning agility. Learning agility reflects the wholesomeness of an individual to impose the skills on the current job one is facing. This is the fundamental ability to learn, adapt, unlearn, and relearn in varied life conditions and scenarios (Mitchinson & Morris, 2014).

Knibbs et al. (2015) opined that employability challenges whether academic and support staff involved in employability and enterprise-related learning, teaching, and support services (e.g., careers and placement offices; incubator, accelerator, and start-up hubs) are fulfilling the needs of all higher education stakeholders.

In this manner, employability appears as an agenda for activating employment expenditures by promoting training programs, services, more or less targeted subsidies that favor hiring or maintenance in the job, and through a varied gamut of incentive or authoritarian measures to put the unemployed back to work. The process is meant to be individualized and preventive, mirrored in the slogan about shifting from job protection to security through employability (Weiner et al., 2017).

The ability of higher education to contribute to employability is, however, an old debate outside the scope of this particular issue. Despite this, the tendency to regard the purpose of education as more than for its own sake puts employability at the center of debates on the social and economic responsibility of higher education (Fakunle & Hingson, 2021).

Clinkard (2019) studied re-conceptualizing higher education employability, where students are encouraged to reflect on their school achievements. The teaching force finds employability very useful for students' development. Likewise, Fletcher-Brown et al. (2015) disclosed that students identified involvement in real live-client projects, applying knowledge learned in the classroom to solve a business problem, enabled them to develop skills demanded by employers. Clients noted how student work exceeded expectations, providing tangible outputs and innovative ideas for their business, even though there were limited periods of interaction. The employability construct represents a scientific challenge to understand better the relationship between job seekers' issues and expectations of the world of work (Guilbert, 2015).

Metacognition is increasingly practiced beyond thinking. Thus, this is essential underpinning institutional programs for the development of teaching in higher education (Henard & Roseveare, 2012). Through the cognitive process, one can do the job, either familiar or unfamiliar with the knowledge they have innately acquired through learning and experiencing. The combination of having the proper knowledge and ability to do something forms a cycle of planning, monitoring, and evaluating (Brown & Lambert, 2012).

Nursing has always been considered to be one of the noblest professions. It has always been regarded as pro-human, and nurses have been known for their selfless caring and tireless service regardless of someone's economic status (Guinid et al., 2019).

The Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) is a four-year program with general education and professional courses. Professional courses are threaded through the first year through the fourth year, emphasizing the nursing concepts with corresponding Related Learning Experience (RLE). The BSN program provides an intensive nursing practice that will refine further the nursing competencies to ensure the achievement of the BSN program outcomes required of an entry-level nurse (Commission on Higher Education [CHED], 2017).

Further, The Commission on Higher Education [CHED] Memorandum Order No. 15, series of 2017, stipulates that the BSN program aims to develop a professional nurse who can assume entry-level positions in health facilities or community settings. The professional nurse is capable of providing safe, human, quality, and holistic care to individuals of varying ages, genders, and health-illness statuses, as well as the health of at-risk families, population groups, and communities, singly or in collaboration with other health care providers to promote health, prevent illness, restore health, alleviate suffering and provide end of life care.

Filipino nurses are in high demand globally because of the standardized and unified nursing curriculum for a Bachelor of Science. This globalized demand leads to the mushrooming of nursing schools, which threatens Filipino nurses' image abroad. Furthermore, this also worsens the country's health services and nursing education (Crisostomo, 2013).

After graduation, graduates are often tasked with a greater responsibility in looking for a job. Crucially, the ability of a graduate to realize or actualize things that he learned from school depends on the individual's personal and external circumstances and the inter-relationship between the two (Tabbuac, 2010). However, students with a low employability level tend to blame the universities' poor and outdated curriculum and the lack of market-driven focus (Tran, 2015).

In previous years, nurses were in demand overseas, driving Filipinos away from the country (Tabbuac, 2010). This global demand for nurses has led to a sudden surge in nursing schools in the Philippines (Bengan, 2011).

This has led to the mass migration of nurses, even prompting doctors to take up nursing. However, there currently needs to be more nurses to be employed here and abroad. Health institutions in the country do not offer new items for hiring nurses. On the other hand, getting their work abroad is complicated and requires many expenses from the nurse who wants to apply (Tabbuac, 2010).

However, institutions mostly need to measure the quality of education they provide. According to a study by Zimmerman (2012), the first two years of college provide almost half of the students with minor learning. Results showed that forty-five percent of the students had no gains in learning. Students were

more focused on their social lives, while their mentors focused more on doing their research than teaching. The study also revealed that among the 3,000 respondents, socializing and sleeping comprise seventy-five percent of their time, while sixteen percent was spent studying.

Pool and Sewel (2007) posit that career development learning has yet to be strongly represented in Higher Education Institutions [HEI's] employability strategies (Johnes, 2006). Training and labor market policymakers decide on the configuration of education and training systems, employment policies, and investments (Ehrenberg et al., 2021).

There is a need to understand and appreciate discipline and how organizations work as skillful practices in academics, employment, and life (Jackson, 2015). Skills reflect professional practices with the implication that this hinges on awareness of and responsiveness to the context in contrast to the narrowly-conceived notions of skills such as appearing at the lower end of the 'essential skills. There is a need to understand the knowledge and skills needed for young professionals to be a more effective and efficient part of the industry (Gerwe, 2021).

Brown and Hesketh (2004) developed and introduced employability in the marketing program in higher education. It employed students to have live-client learning activities in a small to medium enterprise, which enhanced students' economic and local community awareness apart from being employed or having a business. Also, the students should learn to be self-aware in researching the job markets to see what opportunities are available to help them prepare themselves to be more marketable to possible employers (Johnes, 2006).

It is, therefore, important that schools keep track of their graduates to determine the extent of progress they made in their adjustments to the world of work. Further, through follow-up of graduates, some information that suggests the need for improvement of the school program, data essential to continuous appraisal and modification of curriculum, and other services will be gathered (Tabbuac, 2010). The teaching content must be updated, and assessment processes must be streamlined to bring more practical professional knowledge to reduce students' struggles to move from higher education to employment (Mason & Watts, 2009).

Tracer study is a tool used to monitor and evaluate training programs and curricula. It is essential to determine the effectiveness of providing learning and skills to the students. It will help the institution have a basis for areas that need improvement so that students still in the program will acquire better learning experiences (Palomeno et al., 2014).

Conducting graduate tracer studies will help recognize the graduates' needs for improvement and develop a better disposition for those still in the program. Quality and adequacy of staff and good graduate performance will reflect the quality of education (Kebedom, 2010).

Also, conducting tracer studies connects the Alma Mater and the graduates. The graduates could provide their evaluation of the curriculum, learning experiences, and employment status. This helps the institution assess its provision of quality education to produce competent and productive graduates. Tracer studies aim to determine the effectiveness and relevance of the curriculum, the student's learning experiences, and how it affects employment after graduation. This also assesses the employment status of the graduates and how far they have come after earning the knowledge and skills in college (Regmi, 2009).

According to a 1999 graduate tracer study conducted by the Commission on Higher Education, graduates from the University of the Philippines, De La Salle University, and Ateneo de Manila University had lower waiting times in finding a job after graduation, higher employment rates, and higher salaries. Half of the respondents got jobs within six months after graduation, and about one percent of the graduates did not find jobs within two years after graduation. Some reasons for difficulty finding a job were a lack of job opportunities and unsatisfactory salaries. Despite having a college diploma, eighteen percent of college graduates were unemployed from 2006 to 2011. College graduates of medical courses, trade, craft and industrial programs, engineering and architectural programs were the most unemployed graduates. The top three difficult-to-fill positions from January 2009 to June 2010 were accountants and auditors, electronics and communications engineers, and system analysts and designers. These positions had specific technical

requirements and needed to pass an eligible exam. The top three reasons why these positions were difficult to fill were that applicants needed to have the required competency or skill, applicants expected a high salary, and applicants needed years of experience. One factor affecting graduates' employability is the quality of education they received from their higher education institution program (Albert, 2013).

The tracer study of Austria (2023) aimed to improve the nursing program in a state college. The educational profile showed fluctuating nurse licensure examination percentages, and many were not actively involved in continuing professional development. The employment profile showed many graduates without permanent employment status who were not employed in nursing-related jobs. Thus, these findings corroborated the graduates' feedback that a program offering improvement in faculty, curriculum and instruction, library, and physical facilities is needed to produce quality graduates for the labor market.

The study by Du (2019) primarily sought to assess the educational experiences, employment, and achievements of graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing program at LPU–St. Cabrini School of Health Sciences, Inc. from batch 2011-2016. The majority (89.70%) of the nursing graduates at LPU-St. Cabrini are females, single, and employed on a regular status as health practitioners in health facilities. The graduates attested that the college had prepared them to perform as required for an entry-level practitioner with highly developed interpersonal relationship skills, and they believe that motivation to perform efficiently and effectively has been, so far, the best that they have achieved in learning.

The investigation by Sanchez and Diamante (2017) determined the current work status and employment data of the graduates of the University of Cebu Lapulapu and Mandaue (UCLM) College of Nursing of all batches from 2007 to 2014. The findings served as a basis for a report on the employment data of UCnian nursing graduates. The data for this tracer study was gathered through the Graduate Tracer Tool (GTT) patterned from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Descriptive statistics was used in the data analysis. The respondents' employment data showed the nursing graduates' current work status. The majority of the respondents are employed. In their present occupation, most respondents assume professional work and the central line of business is in the health and social work sector. It was depicted that most of them are regular employees, have professional occupations, and have local jobs in the health and social work field. Most are regular/permanent and are locally employed. More than half got their jobs within 1 to 6 months, and almost two-thirds of the respondents had jobs related to the courses they took in college. The competencies that the graduates find helpful in their first job are communication, critical thinking, and human relations skills.

Also, the research of Hipona et al. (2017) tracked the graduates of La Consolacion University Philippines under Bachelor of Science in Nursing from 2016-2020. The descriptive type of research was utilized via online survey questionnaires in Google form as the primary tool to gather the information needed from the respondents. The primary data sources are the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of La Consolacion University Philippines, College of Allied Medical Professions from batch 2016-2020. According to the findings, most graduates work in nursing-related occupations, mainly private institutions. Furthermore, the graduates believe that the BS Nursing program at LCUP has helped them grow emotionally and professionally.

Also, the tracer study by Ofoha and Iwuchukwu (2018) tracked National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) graduate nurses in their workplaces to ascertain their level of professional competency and explore employers' expectations of graduate competencies. The study employed the descriptive survey design. Participants included 222 NOUN alumni who graduated from the nursing program and a corresponding 222 heads/top-level managers of the organizations where the graduate nurses were employed. Data was collected using multiple instruments, including competency tests, survey questionnaires, and direct observation. Several remarkable findings emerged from this study, both expected and unexpected. Most sampled graduates appeared to possess a high level of professional competency in all three measured competency dimensions. A significant proportion of employers seemed to hold a high perception regarding graduates.

Objectives of the Study

This study traced the employability of Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad, School Year 2017-2020 to be able to formulate a proposed program-level intervention plan. Specifically, this study aims to present the following: 1) profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, and civil status; 2) reasons in taking the Bachelor Science in Nursing (BSN) course and professional examination results; 3) trainings and advanced studies attended and reasons for pursuing advanced studies; 4) employment data such as their employment status, the reason for unemployment, place of work, and present occupation; 5) length of time in finding the first job, strategies used to find the first job; 6) gross monthly income; 7) relevance of the curriculum to the first job, competencies learned in college that are useful in the first job, relatedness of the job to college course, and reasons for accepting the job; manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), Manifestation of the attributes stipulated in CMO No. 15 that is specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), and performance of nursing competencies.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussions on the research design, research environment, research respondents, research procedures, treatment of data and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive survey research design to determine the employability of Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad, School Year 2017-2020. A descriptive study is designed to describe the distribution of one or more variables without regard to any causal or other hypothesis (Aggarwal & Ranganathan, 2019). It is concerned with the characteristics of individuals and the characteristics of the whole sample. It provides valuable information on the solutions to local issues (problems). Surveys may be qualitative or quantitative in the verbal or mathematical form of expression; such studies are factual and supply practical information. The survey research employs applications of the scientific method by critically analyzing and examining the source materials, analyzing and interpreting data, and arriving at generalization and prediction (Salaria, 2012).

Research Environment

This study was conducted at organizations or healthcare facilities where the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates were employed during the survey.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the twenty-two (22) Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad from 2017 to July 2020. A convenience sampling technique was used to identify and reach the target respondents.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study is the modified CHED Graduate Tracer Study [GTS] survey questionnaire. This contains questions about the 1) profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, and civil status; 2) reasons in taking the Bachelor Science in Nursing (BSN) course and professional examination results; 3) trainings and advanced studies attended and reasons for pursuing advanced studies; 4) employment data such as their employment status, the reason for unemployment, place of work, and

present occupation; 5) length of time in finding the first job, strategies used to find the first job; 6) gross monthly income; 7) relevance of the curriculum to the first job, competencies learned in college that are useful in the first job, relatedness of the job to college course, and reasons for accepting the job; manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), manifestation of the attributes stipulated in CMO No. 15 that is specific to bachelor of science in nursing, and performance of nursing competencies.

Research Procedure

The researchers sent a letter to the Campus Director and the Dean of the College of Nursing for approval to conduct the study. Another letter was given to the Registrar's Office requesting the overall population of the graduates for the School Year 2017-2020 and asking for authorization to gain access to the latter's contact information, including the home address of the BSN graduates and their landline/cell phone numbers, and email.

Primarily, the administration of the Graduate Tracer Tool (GTS) together with the Informed Consent Form to the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the School Year 2017-2020 was done using the Google Form in which the link was submitted through the Facebook Messenger of the BSN alumni. There were also target respondents who visited the University, and they accomplished the survey tool, and retrieval was done after that.

Treatment of Data

A simple percentage was used to determine the profile of the respondents, while ranking was applied to determine the top utilized academic and nursing competencies learned in college. Weighted mean was used to analyze the data about the manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), manifestation of the attributes stipulated in CMO No. 15 that is specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing, and performance of nursing competencies.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured that the ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and autonomy were adhered to in the conduct. First, orientation about the study was done so that each respondent understood their rights and the nature of the study before being asked to sign the Informed Consent Form (ICF). This protocol was reviewed by the University of Cebu Research Ethics Committee (UCAREC) to obtain the Certificate of Protocol Approval. All the data were handled with utmost confidentiality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, and civil status; 2) reasons in taking the Bachelor Science in Nursing (BSN) course and professional examination results; 3) trainings and advanced studies attended and reasons for pursuing advanced studies; 4) employment data such as their employment status, the reason for unemployment, place of work, and present occupation; 5) length of time in finding the first job, strategies used to find the first job; 6) gross monthly income; 7) relevance of the curriculum to the first job, competencies learned in college that are useful in the first job, relatedness of the job to college course, and reasons for accepting the job; manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), Manifestation of the attributes stipulated in CMO No. 15 that is specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), and performance of nursing competencies. Table 1 and Figure 1 presents the frequency and percentage of each age group.

Table 1. Age of the Respondents (n=22)

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
30 years old and above	5	22.73
28-29 years old	4	18.18
26-27 years old	6	27.27
24-25 years old	7	31.82

Figure 1. Age of the Respondents

Out of the total respondents, seven (7), or 31.82%, belonged to the age bracket of 24 to 25, while the smallest proportion, 18.18%, belonged to the age bracket of 28 to 29 years old. These figures denote that more of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates for the School Year 2017 to 2020 of the University of Cebu-Banilad who responded to the survey were at the young adulthood stage, and these group of alumni graduated a few years ago, and they there still at the initial stage of their career

Figure 2 presents the gender of the respondents.

Table 2. Gender of the Respondents (n= 22)

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Female	18	81.82
Male	4	18.18

Figure 2. Gender of the Respondents

Out of the twenty-two (22) respondents, eighteen (18), or 81.82% of them, were females, while the remaining four (4), or 18.18%, were males. This data indicates that the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) were dominated by ladies since the nursing profession is usually subscribed by women who predominantly have the innate nature to care for patients.

Figure 3 presents the civil status of the respondents.

Table 3. Civil Status of the Respondents (n= 22)

Civil Status	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Single	16	72.73
Married	6	27.27

Figure 3. Civil Status of the Respondents

Sixteen (16), or 72.73% of the respondents were single at the time of the study, while only six (7.12%) were already married. This information indicates that single individuals dominate the respondents since they are still on the verge of starting their nursing profession in the healthcare industry. It can be gleaned

from this information that the BSN graduates were still in their early twenties, and this age is too early to settle down since most Philippine nurses will prepare first to be able to work outside the Philippines.

Figure 4 presents the year the respondents graduated from the University of Cebu-Banilad Campus.

Table 4. Year Graduated of the Respondents (n= 22)

Year	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
2020	6	27.27
2019	8	36.36
2017-2018	5	22.73
2016-2017	3	13.64

Figure 4. Year Graduated of the Respondents

Eight (8) or 38% of the respondents graduated in 2019; the smallest percentage, 13.64 or 3, were graduates in the School Year 2016-2017. This information shows that the group of respondents had graduated five years ago and that they had been working in the various healthcare industry.

Table 5 presents the data about the respondents' reasons for taking the Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] course.

Table 5. Reasons for taking the BSN course for undergraduate degree (n=22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
High grades in the course or subject related to the course	2	7
Influence of parents and relatives	2	7
Peer influence	2	7
Inspired by a role model	4	1
Strong passion for the profession	3	3
Prospect for immediate employment	1	10
Status or prestige of the profession	3	3

Prospect of career advancement	2	7
Prospect of attractive compensation	2	7
Opportunity for employment abroad	3	3

The data shows that the primary reasons respondents took the Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] course are inspired by a role model. In contrast, the other reasons are a strong passion for the profession, status or prestige, and employment opportunities abroad. This information shows that the respondents were motivated to take the Bachelor of Science in Nursing program because the professional nurses inspired them in the different healthcare establishments that provided nursing care.

Table 6 shows the professional examination result of the respondents.

Table 6. Professional Examination Result (n= 22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Passed	17	77.27
Failed	5	22.73

Seventeen (17) respondents, comprising 77.27%, passed the professional examination, and only five (5), or 22.73%, failed the said examination. This information implies that most Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school year 2017-2020 passed the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination [PNLE] after graduation. This indicates that the curriculum and the delivery of educational services enable them to hurdle the rigors of the licensure examinations for nurses.

Table 7 shows the data about the training and advanced studies attended by the respondents after they finished college.

Table 7. Trainings/Advanced Studies Attended after College (n=22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
1.Basic Life Support	4	2
2.Infectious and Communicable Diseases Training Seminar	3	3.5
3.Intravenous Training and Blood Transfusion	5	1
4.New Zealand Diploma Level 7	2	7
5.Private Nurse Training	3	3.5
6.Sacred Heart Hospital Staff Nurse Training	2	7
7.Neonatal Resuscitation Program	2	7
8.Lactation Management Program	1	8.5
9.National Competency II Training - EMS	1	8.5
Reason for Pursuing Advanced Studies:		(%)
1.Promotion	6	27.27
2.Professional Development	16	72.73

The research respondents attended intravenous training and blood transfusion (ranked first), basic life support (ranked second), infectious and communicable diseases training seminar (ranked 3rd), and private nurse training (ranked third). This information indicates that they undertook specialized training in nursing practice to prepare for the real world of nursing practice.

Moreover, they revealed that professional development is the primary reason for pursuing advanced studies. This data denotes that after graduating with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree and passing the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination [PNLE], they focused on enhancing their abilities to deliver nursing care, mainly when they are employed in the hospital and other health institutions.

Table 8 presents the data about the present employment status of the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 8. Present Employment Status of the Graduates (n = 22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Regular or Permanent	10	45.45
Temporary	3	13.64
Casual	2	9.09
Contractual	6	27.27
Self-employed	1	4.55

Ten (10), or 45.45% of the graduate respondents, had a regular or permanent employment status, while only one (1), or equivalent of 4.55%, was self-employed. This information implies that more Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad were employed at healthcare establishments after they passed the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination [PNLE] and obtained their licenses as professional nurses.

Table 9 presents the data about the respondents' reasons for unemployment.

Table 9. Reasons for Unemployment of the Graduates (n = 10)

Indicators	Frequency(f)	Rank
Advance or further studies	7	1
No job opportunity	2	2
Did not look for job	1	3

* Multiple response

For the ten (10) respondents who were not working or unemployed at the time of the survey, their foremost reason for their unemployment was that they were still taking advanced or further studies (ranked first), no job opportunity (ranked second), and the did not look for job (ranked third). This data implies that those who were unemployed they tend to focus their time on advancing their nursing competencies before they embark on practicing their nursing profession.

Table 10 presents the place of work of the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing.

Table 10. Place of Work of the Respondents (n = 22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Local	19	86.36
Abroad	3	13.64

Of the twenty-two (22) Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates, nineteen (19), or 86.36%, worked here in the Philippines, while only three (3) or 13.64% worked abroad. Since the respondents graduated 4 to 7 years ago, they were still obtaining hospital or relevant experience in the field of nursing before they sought overseas employment like in Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates (UAE), Singapore, or go to the United States (US) United Kingdom (UK), Australia, New Zealand, or even to Canada to earn higher salaries compared to the amount they can earn if they work in Philippine hospitals or healthcare facilities and have better life including their family.

Table 11 presents the line of business of the company of the graduate's first job.

Table 11. Present Occupation of the Nursing Graduates (n=22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
○ Officials of Government and Special-interest Organizations, Corporate Executives, Managers, Managing Proprietors and Supervisors	5	22.73
○ Professionals	13	59.09
○ Clerks	2	9.09
○ Service workers and Shop/Market Sales workers	1	4.55
○ Special Occupation	1	4.55

Of the twenty-two (22) respondents, thirteen (13), or 59.09%, worked as professionals. In contrast, one (1), or 4.55% of the respondents, was employed as a service worker and shop/market sales worker, and the other one (1), or 4.55%, had a particular occupation. This data shows that most Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu- Banilad were engaged in work that aligns with their discipline, especially as professional nurses in the healthcare provider establishment, primarily the hospital.

Table 12 shows the data on the length of time the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad were able to find a job.

Table 12. Length of Time in Finding the First Job (n=22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Less than a month	8	36.36
1 to 6 months	7	31.82
7 to 11 months	3	13.64
1 year to less than 2 years	0	0
2 years to less than 3 years	0	0
3 years to less than 4 years	4	18.18

Eight (8), or 36.36% of the graduates, could find their first job in less than a month, while three (3), or 13.64% of the graduates, could find a job in 7 to 11 months. This means that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad were highly employable in the healthcare industry and could exercise their nursing profession. Additionally, they can find employment that aligns with their field of discipline in less than a year due to the high demand for nurses in many healthcare establishments in the Philippines and even abroad like the middle eastern nations, United Kingdom, United States, Singapore, Australia, New Zealand, and many more.

Table 13 presents the frequency distribution of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates in terms of how they find their first job.

Seven (7), or 31.82%, of the graduates found their first job through a recommendation by someone, while two (2), or 9.09%, found through job fairs, and another two (2), or 9.09% were arranged by the school's Job Placement Officer.

Table 13. Strategies Used to Find the First Job (n = 22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Response to an advertisement	3	13.64
As walk-in applicant	3	13.64
Recommended by someone	7	31.82
Information from friends	5	22.73
Arranged by school's job placement officer	2	9.09
Job Fair	2	9.09

These survey results mean that Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad could find their jobs through their social circle and did not depend on the university's job fair activities to enable them to find employment.

Table 14 presents the gross monthly income of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 14. Gross Monthly Income of the Graduates (n= 58)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Php 25,000.00 and above	5	22.73
Php 20,000.00 - below Php 25,000.00	10	45.45
Php 15,000.00 - below Php 20,000.00	3	13.64
Php 10,000.00 - below Php 15,000.00	2	9.09
Php 5,000.00 - below Php 10,000.00	2	9.09

Ten (10) or 45.45% of the respondent graduates earned a gross monthly income of Php20,000.00 to below Php 25,000.00. At the same time, only two (2) or 9.09% earned Php 5,000.00-below Php 10,000.00, and another two (2) or 9.09% of graduate-respondents earned a gross monthly income of Php 10,000.00- below Php 15, 000.00. These results imply that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad earned a salary above the minimum wage. This level of

income is considered an entry-level for nursing professionals, but very low compared to the amount of salary that they can earn if they work abroad,

However, few received low salaries and/or compensation, which was not commensurate to the daily expenses that a family of five needed. For the usual family size of Filipinos, they pay at least ₱5,590.00 on average every month (for last year to meet basic food needs and at least ₱8,022.00 on average monthly to meet both basic and non-food needs for the current year. Hence, this explains that the majority of the nursing professionals in the Philippines tend to work and migrate abroad to have a better life,

Table 15 presents the data about the respondents' assessments of the relevance of the curriculum to the first job..

Table 15. Relevance of the Curriculum to the First Job (n = 58)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	15	68.18
No	7	31.82

Fifteen (15), or 68.18% of the respondents, revealed that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) curriculum that they took at the University of Cebu-Banilad was related to their job. Only seven (7), or 31.82%, said their current work is irrelevant to their college curriculum. Currently, nurses are in demand in most hospitals in the Philippines and abroad. Hence, it is easy for a nursing professional to land a job.

Understandably, these respondents worked in an industry unrelated to nursing practice or discipline. Therefore, they cannot infer that their learning in college is directly connected to the performance of their first job.

Table 16 shows the competencies learned that are useful in the first job of the graduate respondents.

Table 16. Competencies Learned in that are Useful in the First Job (n = 58)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
Communication Skills	21	1
Human Relations Skills	18	2
Entrepreneurial Skills	10	5
Information Technology Skills	13	4
Problem Solving Skills	17	3.5
Critical Thinking Skills	17	3.5

**Multiple Responses*

The Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad learned communication skills (ranked first), human relations skills (ranked second), problem-solving skills, and critical thinking skills (ranked third). This data implies that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing curriculum at the University of Cebu-Banilad strengthens the students' hard skills and soft skills, which are very useful in job interviews and in taking higher career levels as nursing professionals. These responses also indicate

that the BSN graduates viewed the educational services provided to them as enhancing their nursing competencies, including their ability to communicate and relate to other people, which are helpful in their jobs. Nevertheless, there is a need to strengthen their entrepreneurial and information technology skills, which are vital in the real world of work and career advancement in the healthcare industry.

Table 17 shows the data concerning the respondents' assessments of the relatedness of the job to the college course.

Table 17. Relatedness of the Job to the College Course (n= 22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	16	72.73
No	6	27.27

Sixteen (16), or equivalent to 72.73% of the respondents, answered that their undergraduate degree was relevant to their current job. In contrast, only six (6) respondents, or 27.27%, said their course was unrelated to their current job. These results mean that knowledge learned by the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates in the different subjects they took while studying at the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) University of Cebu-Banilad is applicable in the course of their performance in their job.

Table 18 shows the respondents' reasons for accepting the job.

Table 18. Reasons for Accepting the Job (n = 22)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
Salaries & benefits	22	1st
Career Challenge	15	3rd
Related to special skills	19	2nd
Proximity to residence	10	4th

**Multiple Responses*

Twenty-two (22) respondents answered that they considered accepting the because of the salaries and benefits (ranked first), then related to their unique skills (ranked second), and then career challenge (ranked third). Understandably, the primordial consideration for any graduate looking for a job is its relatedness to their bachelor's degree since they can efficiently perform the job since they have specialized knowledge from school.

This section presents the data concerning the manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, and goals, Program Educational Objectives [PEO}, and Program Outcomes (PO) by the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu-Banilad. The data are presented in tabular form.

Table 19 shows the respondents' manifestation of the College of Nursing Vision.

Table 19. Respondents' Manifestation of the College of Nursing Vision (n= 22)

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
A leading provider of accessible and quality nursing education and producing globally competent nurses.	3.86	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00-Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested;

1.00 -1.75 - Not Manifested

The weighted mean of 3.86 shows that the respondents divulged that they manifested to a great extent the vision of the University of Cebu- Banilad College of Nursing (BSN) of Nursing to become a leading producer of accessible and quality nursing. The attainment of such a vision lies in the manifestation of high nursing competencies and skills among BSN graduates for the school years 2017 to 2020. Their excellent abilities in their respective jobs mirror the University of Cebu's competencies in producing quality professional nurses who are globally-competent. This means that the educational training provided by the University of Cebu lead their graduated to become proficient in nursing skills even in the global healthcare arena.

Table 20 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attribute stipulated in the mission statement of the College of Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad.

The weighted mean of 3.77 indicates that the respondents divulged that they manifested to a great extent the attributes of being graduates of the University of Cebu- Banilad that aims to maintain a healthy educational setting that fosters quality performance, satisfaction, and life-long learning through research-based instruction and community extension. This means that the Bachelor of Science (BSN) affords holistic student development that encompasses the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor components of educational training.

Table 20. Respondents' Manifestation of the Mission of the College of Nursing (n=22)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Maintain a healthy educational setting which fosters quality performance, satisfaction and life-long learning through research-based instruction and community extension	3.77	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

This information further denotes that educational training provided to the BSN students is evidenced-based and that the curriculum is regularly revisited, reviewed, and revised based on the changes in the CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] and the University of Cebu strategic direction and standards.

Table 21 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the College of Nursing Goals.

Table 21. Respondents' Manifestation of the College of Nursing Goals (n=22)

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Adapt competency standards in instruction learning resources, and educational services	3.90	Greatly Manifested
2. Promote leadership among faculty in the service of the community.	3.86	Greatly Manifested
3. Foster a pool of highly motivated competent and compassionate faculty and students in the pursuit of personal and professional development	3.90	Greatly Manifested
Aggregate Mean	3.87	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51-3.25- Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents divulged that they manifested to a great extent the attributes of adapting competency standards in instruction, learning resources, and educational services. This indicates that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu-Banilad recognized that the quality of educational training provided to them enabled them to grasp and practice the theories of nursing and exhibited them in actual practice since they were exposed to the tenets of hospital duty. Also, there were sessions in which they had simulation learning activities at the Nursing Skills Laboratory.

Another highest weighted mean of 3.90 specifies that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attribute of fostering a pool of highly motivated, competent, and compassionate faculty and students in the pursuit of personal and professional development. The University of Cebu administration hired only qualified professional nurses as faculty members. This means the pool of nurse educators at least have a master's degree relevant to the nursing discipline. These results mean that the University of Cebu-Banilad's educational system was appreciated by the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates since they became well-rounded and competent nurses.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.86 indicates that the respondents disclosed to a great extent the attributes of being a graduate of the University of Cebu-Banilad that promotes leadership among faculty in the service of the community. One of the four focal functions of the University of Cebu is community extension, which is practiced along with instruction, research, and production. The values of community services at UC enabled both the faculty members and the students to assess the real needs of the adopted community, the Barangay Apas, Cebu City, in which the activities and programs enabled them to provide help to the real needs of the marginalized sector of the community. This way, they could apply what they learned in class to those needing it.

The aggregate mean of 3.87 shows that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attributes stipulated in the College of Nursing goals. Based on the experiences of the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), the University of Cebu-Banilad was successful in providing holistic educational services and programs that molded and trained students to become competent in the hospitality industry and even in other industries since they are well-rounded and flexible.

Table 22 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the core values of the College of Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 22. Respondents' Manifestation of the College of Nursing Core Values (n=22)

	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1.	Nurturing	3.81	Greatly Manifested
2.	Unity	3.77	Greatly Manifested
3.	Respect	3.86	Greatly Manifested
4.	Service	3.77	Greatly Manifested
5.	Excellence	3.82	Greatly Manifested
	Aggregate Mean	3.81	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.86 shows that the respondents divulged that they manifested to a great extent the attributes of being respectful. It can be gleaned that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing for the school years 2017 to 2020 exhibited politeness and consideration for the wellbeing of others.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.77 indicates that the respondents disclosed that they manifested to a great extent the value of unity. This means that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing for the abovementioned school years exhibited collaboration, cooperation, and camaraderie in their actions, especially in the context of performing their actions in their current job, which entails coordinating with work colleagues.

Another lowest weighted mean of 3.77 indicates that the respondents disclosed that they manifested to a great extent the value of service, which entails exhibiting altruistic behavior in which they help those who are in need, regardless of discrimination and bias. This means they can practice helping anyone regardless of race, culture, relation, socio-economic status, or affiliation.

The aggregate mean of 3.81 shows that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attributes stipulated in the core values of the College of Nursing, such as nurturing, unity, respect, service, and excellence. These core values were embedded in the curriculum and the delivery of instructional services. They are also explicitly included in all the curricular and extra-curricular activities undertaken by the College of Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad as an institution.

Table 23 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing.

Table 23. Respondents 'Manifestation of the BSN Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) (n=22)

	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1.	demonstrate knowledge and skills in client care management in accordance with the Nurse's Code of Ethics and Legal Principles.	3.82	Greatly Manifested
2.	practice as caring and compassionate clinical, community health, occupational health, private duty, and entrepreneurial nurses.	3.82	Greatly Manifested
3.	integrate research findings to improve client care.	3.82	Greatly Manifested
	Aggregate Mean	3.82	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The mean of 3.82 shows that the respondents divulged that the respondents revealed that they demonstrated knowledge and skills in client care management in accordance with the Nurse's Code of Ethics and Legal Principles to a great extent. It can be denoted that they can manage all aspects of caring and show concern and appreciation for the clients while providing quality services to them.

Moreover, the mean of 3.82 shows that the respondents divulged that they practiced the value of caring and compassionate clinical, community health, occupational health, private duty, and entrepreneurial nurses. This indicates that the BSN graduates exhibited the attributes of showing and providing care to the clients in various or whatever aspects of being a professional nurse, like delivering health programs and services to community groups and employees, providing service to those who need the extra assistance but prefer to live at home instead of in skilled nursing care facilities and healthcare knowledge and business sensibilities to develop successful business ventures that center around optimal care delivery.

Further, the mean of 3.82 shows the respondents divulged that they integrated research findings to improve client care. This means that the BSN graduates of UC-Banilad can research since they have undergone training as part of the curriculum and can use what they have learned to improve their decisions and actions in adjusting to the varying needs of their clients or patients.

The aggregate mean of 3.82 shows that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attributes stipulated in Program Educational Objectives (PEO) for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad. It can be gleaned that the curriculum and the educational activities of the school prepared them to achieve career and professional accomplishments for the BSN program.

Hence, the graduates of the BSN program of UC-Banilad have the competencies and abilities to exhibit the standards of nursing practice to provide patient care in all contexts and environments. Also, they can improve the quality of nursing service based on the changes and requirements of the healthcare establishment, regulatory bodies, or when needed.

Table 24 shows the respondents' assessments on the attainment of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program Outcomes (POs).

Table 24. Respondents' Attainment of the BSN Program Outcomes (POs)

	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1.	pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Exam (PNLE).	3.77	Highly Attained
2.	apply the nursing process and accurate documentation system in the interdisciplinary care of clients.	3.90	Highly Attained
3.	observe the core values, bioethical principles and legal awareness cherished by the Nursing profession in the care of clients.	3.86	Highly Attained
4.	engage in activities that promote professional and personal development.	3.86	Highly Attained
5.	participate in the development of policies and standards utilizing evidence-based practice.	3.86	Highly Attained

6.	apply principles of partnership and collaboration to improve delivery of health care services .	3.82	Highly Attained
	Aggregate Mean	3.85	Highly Attained

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Highly Attained; 2.51 -3.25-Moderately Attained; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Attained; 1.00 -1.75 - Not Attained

The highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents assessed that they applied the nursing process and accurate documentation system in the interdisciplinary care of clients to a great extent. These results mean that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad can perform appropriate client or patient records or documentation while minding the appropriate data privacy and confidentiality. The BSN students were trained and exposed to the available information, communication technology (ICT), or automated documentation systems, which enabled them as healthcare professionals to develop dynamic, interdisciplinary care plans that are linked to clinical charting and the documentation of outcomes.

The quality of the nursing graduates of an educational institution is the best evaluative tool for the quality of education the school provides (Banua, 2017). On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.77 indicates that the respondents disclosed that, to a great extent, they passed the Philippine Nurse Licensure Exam (PNLE). The BSN curriculum of UC-Banilad enabled the graduates to pass the licensure examination required to become professional nurses successfully. So, the appropriate implementation of the admission and retention policies for the BSN program of the University of Cebu-Banilad while instituting effective teaching-learning strategies to assist the students in achieving excellent academic performance led them to pass the PNLE.

The aggregate mean of 3.85 shows that the respondents assessed that BSN's Program Outcomes (PO) were highly attained. The graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program at the University of Cebu-Banilad viewed that they learned the various learning competencies that are needed in the actual practice of professional nurses in whatever field. Further, they knew they could acquire the knowledge skills when they satisfactorily obtained the BSN degree.

Table 25 shows the respondents' responses to their manifestation of the stipulations in the CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15, 2017, series for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] program.

Table 25. Respondents' Manifestation of the Attributes Stipulated in CMO No. 15 Specific for Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program (n=22)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
<i>A graduate of a BSN degree should be able to:</i>		
1. apply knowledge of physical, social, natural and health sciences, and humanities in the practice of nursing.	3.73	Greatly Manifested
2. perform safe, appropriate, and holistic care to individual families, population groups and community utilizing process	3.77	Greatly Manifested
3. apply guidelines and principles of evidence-based practice in the delivery of care.	3.90	Greatly Manifested

4.	practice nursing in accordance with existing laws, legal, ethical and moral principles	3.90	Greatly Manifested
5.	communicate effectively in speaking, writing and presenting using culturally-appropriate language.	3.77	Greatly Manifested
6.	document to include reporting up-to-date client care accurately and comprehensively.	3.86	Greatly Manifested
7.	collaborate effectively in collaboration with inter-, intra- and multi-disciplinary and multi-cultural teams.	3.82	Greatly Manifested
8.	practice beginning management and leadership skills in delivery of client care using a systems approach.	3.77	Greatly Manifested
9.	conduct research with an experienced researcher.	3.45	Greatly Manifested
10.	engage in lifelong learning with a passion to keep current with and global development in general, and nursing and health developments in particular.	3.77	Greatly Manifested
11.	demonstrate responsible citizenship and pride in being a Filipino.	3.86	Greatly Manifested
	apply techno-intelligent care systems and health care delivery.	3.86	Greatly Manifested
11.	uphold the nursing core values in the practice of profession.	3.95	Greatly Manifested
12.	apply entrepreneurial skills in the delivery of nursing care.	3.82	Greatly Manifested
Aggregate Mean		3.80	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 - 2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.95 shows that the respondents divulged, to a great extent, that they upheld the nursing core values in the practice of the profession. These results mean that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu-Banilad learned and applied values that guide nurses to advocate for patient welfare, respect patient autonomy and decisions, value human worth and uniqueness, act with honesty and ethics, and support equal access to healthcare.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.45 indicates that the respondents disclosed that they, to a great extent, conducted research with an experienced researcher. Part of the BSN curriculum is research in which they are required to engage in nursing and health-related research, make evaluations of research studies, and apply the research process in improving client care. Moreover, the students were taught about the research methods and designs, and then they were required to prepare a research protocol they would implement. This curricular requirement enabled them to experience the rigors of doing and writing research related to the nursing discipline across different fields of concentration. This

The aggregate mean of 3.80 shows that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attributes stipulated in CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15 for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates, particularly on the expected roles and career that they can engage once they satisfactorily completed the program requirements like provision of client care, serving as managers and leaders in nursing service units and health services and programs, and engagement in research.

Table 27 shows the data about the respondents' manifestation of the performance indicators for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] program as stipulated in the CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15, Series of 2017.

Table 27. Respondents' Manifestation of the Performance Indicators for BSN in CMO No. 15, Series of 2017 (n=22)

No.	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.	Integrating relevant principles of social, physical, natural and health sciences and humanities in a given health and nursing education.	3.77	Greatly Manifested
2.	Applying appropriate nursing concepts and actions holistically and comprehensively.	3.86	Greatly Manifested
3.	Assessing with the client (individual, family, population group, and/or community), one's health.	3.82	Greatly Manifested
4.	Formulating with the client a plan of care to address the health conditions, needs, problems and issues.	3.90	Greatly Manifested
5.	Implementing safe and quality interventions with the client to address the health needs, problems and issues.	3.90	Greatly Manifested
Aggregate Mean		3.85	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested ; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents shared that, to a great extent, they can formulate a plan of care to address their health conditions, needs, problems, and issues. This means that the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing of the University of Cebu-Banilad (UC-B) are capable of making a care plan that includes six components: assessment, diagnosis, expected outcomes, interventions, rationale, and evaluation, which details a safe and effective routine for the individual in question based on their personal preferences, beliefs, and unique situation.

Another highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents divulged that, to a great extent, they could implement safe and quality interventions with the client to address the health needs, problems, and issues; they also powerfully manifested in formulating with the client a plan of care to address the health conditions, needs, problems, and issues. It can be deduced that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad possessed excellent skills in implementing their patient care plan, including any treatments, procedures, or teaching moments intended to improve the patient's comfort and health.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.77 indicates that the respondents disclosed that, to a great extent, they could integrate relevant social, physical, natural, and health sciences and humanities principles in a given health and nursing education. The primordial goal of the BSN curriculum is to train the students on the various principles of providing care to clients so that when they finish the program and become registered nurses, they can demonstrate and apply these principles in providing quality and well-rounded services.

The aggregate mean of 3.85 shows that the respondents revealed that, to a great extent, they manifested the competencies of professional nurses. Thereby, it can be inferred that the graduates of the BSN program of UC-Banilad can provide holistic and safe client care based on the norms.

Conclusions

Therefore, the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program of UC-Banilad for the school years 2017-2020 were employable across various healthcare industry establishments, enabling them to practice their nursing profession across varying nursing fields. Likewise, they exhibited the nurse's desired competencies and graduate attributes as indicated in the BSN curriculum, the CHED Memorandum Order No. 15, series of 2017, and the University's strategic direction. This also indicated that the BSN curriculum of UC is in line with the established requirements by the regulatory bodies and the requirements of the healthcare industry in the Philippines and even in other countries where they currently work.

Translational Research

About the significant findings of this investigation, a program-level intervention plan shall be devised to encompass regular review and revision of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) curriculum of the University of Cebu to ensure that it is compliant with the regulatory standards and addresses the current healthcare industry requirements. It shall integrate feasible programs and activities to ensure nursing education that aligns with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) requirements, hospital partners, the healthcare industry, and the community where the graduates will exercise their nursing profession. Also, the plan shall intensify measures in preparing the students to pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination (PNLE) and other examinations that they will take in the future for a promising nursing career here in the Philippines and abroad.

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